

Chemical and Physical Characteristics of Organic Particulate Matter from Exhaust After-treatment System of Euro 6 Diesel Engine Operating at Full Load

Author, co-author (**Do NOT enter this information. It will be pulled from participant tab in MyTechZone**)

Affiliation (**Do NOT enter this information. It will be pulled from participant tab in MyTechZone**)

Abstract

The current legislation does not take into account the limitation of sub 23 nm particles from engine. Nevertheless, the Common Rail Diesel engine emits a large number of nanoparticle, solid and volatiles, that are very dangerous for human health. In this contest, the challenge of the “dieper EU project” is to apply advanced technologies for exhaust after-treatment to existing diesel engines and to optimize the characteristics of a new generation of engines with regards to emissions, fuel consumption and drivability.

Aim of the present paper is to provide useful information for the development of the after-treatment system that will have to fulfill Euro6 further steps. In order to characterize the chemical and physical nature of Particulate Matter emitted from Euro 6b Medium Duty diesel engine, the pollutants were collected and analyzed: from engine-out, downstream of the particulate filter (DPF), and at the exit of a selective catalytic reactor (SCR). An array of chemical, physical and spectroscopic techniques (Gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (GC-MS), mobility analyzer, UV-visible absorption and fluorescence spectroscopy) was applied for characterizing the organic particulate matter (PM, constituted of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH), heavy aromatic compounds, soot) in the exhaust line. The engine was operated in full-load condition (100% of the accelerator pedal position, representing the best performance of the engine operation) at different engine speeds.

Results showed that the abatement efficiency of soot after DPF and SCR systems, at all engine speeds, is very high (around 90% or more), as evaluated gravimetrically and by mobility analyzer, which discriminates also among the different dimensional ranges of particles. The DPF is more efficient at collecting <23nm than >23nm particles whereas in the SCR system particles are subjected to reactions which seem to support an agglomeration of particles, with beneficial effect on the harmfulness to human health. For PAH the abatement efficiency is lower with respect to soot, but it increases at higher engine speeds, when the concentration is much higher.

Introduction

In the last period, European Community has shown strong interest in the understanding and measurement of the PM particles from the internal combustion engines (ICE). Several EU projects have been financed: DownToTen [1], Soreal-23 [2], PEMS4Nano [3], dieper [4]

et al. in order to choose the best way to characterize the particles, with particular attention to those below 23 nm, in terms of measurement instruments and after treatment systems. In particular, the main objective of “dieper project” has been to develop new technology for the reduction of sub 23 nm particles from diesel engines of vehicle manufacturing sectors. The involved industries and research centers have been developed the knowhow, intellectual property rights and technical capabilities to adequately and cost-effectively produce cleaner, highly efficient Diesel powertrains and after-treatment technologies for future class D and E passenger cars and light commercial vehicles (LCVs) up to 3,500 kg that “go beyond Euro 6 limits under Real Driving conditions” (EU6 RDE).

The main reason of the Europe Union (EU) interest is because ultrafine particles (smaller than 0.1 μm) have been associated with adverse health effects and act through mechanisms not shared with larger particles [5]. Actually, the legislation limits only the counting of solid (non-volatile) particles larger than 23 nm. A minimum diameter of 23 nm size was selected in order to include the smallest soot particles and exclude volatile nucleation mode particles. Volatile particles were excluded in order to improve the repeatability and reproducibility of the measurement to levels acceptable for legislative purposes [6]. Thus, there is the necessity to deeper the knowledge of these particles under 23 nm in terms of physical and chemical characterization.

On the other hand, the certification procedure for new vehicles (or engines) around the world is accomplished by applying a driving cycle. Until September 2017 the passenger cars pollutant emissions were regulated by Euro 6b limits that are based on the New European Driving Cycle (NEDC). Beyond September 2017, Euro6d enters into force for new type approvals which claims the same emission limits under the changed test procedures of the World-wide harmonized Light duty Test Cycle (WLTC) and the new World-wide harmonized Light-duty Test Procedure (WLTP). These tests were born from the necessity of reproducing the driving situation closer to the actual working conditions of a vehicle. The WLTC is a suite of cycles, with different speed/time schedules depending on the tested vehicle’s power to mass ratio (PMR). It is characterized by relatively long duration (of the order of 20–30 min) under varying operating conditions, cold or hot starting, including (for highway engines/vehicles) urban as well as motorway driving. In fact, the most frequent daily driving (transient) conditions must be encompassed in the certification procedure to certify the new vehicles tested on chassis dynamometer or engines on test bed. For this reason, the most realistic configuration to release the certification for

a vehicle is to collect data from on-board diagnostics (OBD) and portable emissions measurement systems (PEMS) when driving under real-world conditions (RDE). Even if the real operating conditions are fundamental for the evaluation of exhaust after treatment systems (EATS) on a vehicle; unfortunately, the possibility to study carefully the exhaust gases from the engine and, in conjunction, the efficiency of the several components of an exhaust pipe line of a vehicle cannot be achieved with the engine running in transient condition. For this reason, in the present paper, the engine run at Full Load (FL) sweeping the engine speeds in steady state condition. The FL operating condition was chosen in order to characterize the EATS performance and efficiency in the worst stress conditions. By this procedure, it has been possible to recognize the physical and chemical characteristics of the soot in the raw exhaust gas and passing through diesel particulate filter (DPF) and/or selective catalytic reactor (SCR).

Finally, due to the lack of information about the effect on the PM that flows through SCR and due to the increasingly interest in the development of SCR on filter (SCR-F), the effect of after-treatment system for the abatement of NOx on organic PM has been studied.

The comparison of soot and PAH concentrations, size distribution and chemical speciation in the different engine operation conditions allowed understanding that the abatement efficiency of soot after DPF and SCR systems, at all engine speeds, is very high (around 90% or more), as evaluated gravimetrically and by mobility analyzer, which discriminates also among the different dimensional ranges of particles. The DPF is more efficient at collecting <23nm than >23nm particles whereas in the SCR system particles are subjected to reactions which seem to support an agglomeration of particles, with beneficial effect on the harmfulness to human health. For PAH the abatement efficiency is lower with respect to soot, but it increases at higher engine speeds, when the concentration is much higher.

Experimental

Experimental apparatus

The Diesel engine set up in the laboratory of Istituto Motori is from medium duty E6b vehicle whose characteristics are shown in Table 1. The maximum torque level of the engine is 430 Nm, whilst the rated power is at 132 kW. The new vehicle with the numeration E6 is a light commercial vehicle with a swept volume of 3 liters. This model year 2016 engine fulfils Euro 6b standards, inter alia by the use of both Exhaust Gas Recirculation (EGR) and SCR systems.

Table 1. Engine characteristics

Engine	F1C
Number of cylinders	4
Swept volume	2998 cm ³
Bore x Stroke	95.8 x 104 mm
Rated Power @ Engine speed	132 kW @ 3000 rpm
Max Torque @ Engine speed	430 Nm @ 2865 rpm
Injection system	DI-CR max inject. press 1800 bar
Emission level	Euro 6b

The engine configuration for the E6b standards fulfillment is equipped with a diesel oxidation catalyst (DOC) + passive Diesel Particle Filter (DPF) system in the same canister and with a Selective Catalytic Reactor & Clean-Up Catalyst (SCR+CUC) system mounted downstream. The DOC is devoted to oxidation of HC, CO, and PM and to the conversion of NO into NO₂, while in the DPF the PM oxidation occurs by means of NO₂ and O₂. After the DPF, a urea injector is set up to provide NH₃ by hydrolysis from urea to activate the catalytic reactions of the SCR and to reduce the NOx via ammonia. Finally, ammonia is reduced exiting from the SCR in the CUC. In Fig. 1, the DOC+DPF system is shown. In Fig. 2, the layout of the SCR+CUC system is reported. The sampling of the exhaust has been performed before the after-treatment systems (in the following indicated with B-DPF) and in two locations in the after-treatment systems: after the DPF (in the following indicated with A-DPF) prior to the urea injector location, and after the SCR (A-SCR).

The engine is installed on alternating current (AC) transient dynamometer and is set up to reproduce the real operating conditions. Temperature and humidity are controlled, the engine parameters and exhaust emissions are monitored and measured both with the sensors installed by the engine manufacturer and with additional sensors installed for the experimental campaign.

In-cylinder combustion evolution was monitored via a piezoelectric pressure transducer, the measured in-cylinder pressure, and the computed rate of heat release and combustion temperature were useful to provide information on the in-cylinder pollutants formation.

Fig. 1: Image of the exhaust line from the engine-out immediately down the turbo compressor up to the exit from the DPF.

Fig. 2: Image of the exhaust line for the AdBlue injection and mixing up to the exit of the SCR.

The sampling was performed at four different engine speeds (1600, 2000, 3000, 3500) and at maximum rated power (FL, 100% of the accelerator pedal position), which represents the best performance of the engine operation and the worst stress conditions for the operation of the after-treatment systems.

For the chemical analysis, the sampling line was constituted by an ice-cooled trap to collect condensed species and a Teflon filter to collect particles. A liquid-liquid extraction using Dichloromethane (DCM) was used to separate the soluble organic fraction (SOF) condensed in the ice trap from water. Also the Teflon filter was washed with DCM to solubilize the SOF adsorbed on soot particles. SOF solubilized in DCM obtained by Teflon filter and ice trap extraction procedures were joined together and the volume of the solvent was reduced to 0.5 ml for performing gas chromatography mass spectrometry (GC/MS) and spectroscopic analysis. Soot was dried and weighed. Soot size distribution was also on-line measured by a mobility analyzer.

Analytical techniques

Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS). The GC-MS employed is an AGILENT GC 7890 - MSD 5975C. In the GC, a HP-35 (length 30 m, i.d. 250 μ m, film 0.25 μ m) column is mounted. Sample injection was done in splitless mode at 300 °C with a gas flow of 1 ml/min (STP). The temperature program consists of four isothermal steps: 323 K (5 min), constant heating for 30 min to 473 K (5 min), constant heating for 1.75 min to 543 K (5 min) and finally, constant heating for 6 min to 573 K (15 min). The transfer line between the GC and the MS is held at 573 K. The mass spectrometer operated in electron ionization mode, and m/z was scanned from 50 to 400. The concentration of PAH is quantified using known factors calculated from the analysis of a standard sample of known concentrations (PAH mixture with MW up to 300 Da supplied by Supelco EPA 525 PAH mix; C16 and phenol sample from Sigma Aldrich).

UV-visible absorption. UV-Vis spectra of the samples, dissolved in DCM, were measured on an HP 8453 Diode Array spectrophotometer using 1 cm quartz cuvettes.

UV-visible fluorescence. Fluorescence spectra were acquired on a PerkinElmer LS-50 spectrofluorometer. The wavelength accuracy was ± 1.0 nm, and the wavelength reproducibility was ± 0.5 nm.

Mobility analyzer. For particulate measurement, a Cambustion DMS 500 fast particulate analyzer was used which combines electrical mobility measurements of particles with sensitive electrometer detectors, allowing generation of particle size/number distributions in real-time. These outputs are further processed to give simultaneous outputs of particle size, number and mass. The DMS 500 is fitted with a fully integrated two-stage dilution. This provides 1st dilution at the point of sampling to avoid condensation and agglomeration, and a higher factor 2nd diluter to allow sampling from a very wide range of aerosol concentrations. The DMS 500 uses a high voltage discharge to charge each particle proportional to its surface area. Charged particles are introduced into a classification section with a strong radial electrical field. This field causes particles to drift through a sheath flow toward the electrometer detectors. Particles are detected at different distances down the column, depending upon their aerodynamic drag/charge ratio. Outputs from the 22 electrometers are processed in real-time at 10 Hz to provide spectral data and other metrics. Particulate size distributions are displayed

real-time and recorded for the entire test duration. The data are post processed providing all the size distributions stored, and the statistical data as number, mass and size of particles. At the test points after the DPF and after SCR, the DR was kept constant to 5 for all the operating conditions. For the test point at engine out, DR was set up at 1000.

Results and discussion

The engine was set up at Istituto Motori laboratory to fulfill the maximum torque and power, Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Maximum engine torque and power of the F1C engine versus the engine speeds

Fig. 4: Temperature engine out, downstream DPF, upstream and downstream SCR of the F1C engine at Full Load

Temperatures measured before DPF (B-DPF), after DPF (A-DPF), and before and after SCR (B-SCR & A-SCR) are reported in Fig. 4; as expected increasing engine speed increases the temperature at the engine out. Passing through the DOC and DPF a slight increase in the temperature is noted due to the chemical reactions occurring to oxidize the HC and CO into the DOC and due to the regeneration of the DPF. Temperatures B-SCR are lower due to the urea injection; and, finally, the lower temperature are measured at the exit of the SCR and CUC systems.

Soot and SOF concentrations sampled at engine out, prior the exhaust gas enters the DOC+DPF, for all the tested conditions are reported in Fig. 5. The maximum soot and minimum SOF amount was obtained at 3000 rpm that corresponds at maximum engine power. At higher engine speeds, the maximum injection pressure (1800 bar) and the combustion development strongly influence the in-cylinder soot formation reducing the SOF in the collected sample. At lower engine speeds, the multi-injection strategy, affect the in-cylinder combustion cycle, as well as the in-cylinder temperature and, then, the soot

formation. Therefore, at the exhaust, the PM is made by low soot while the SOF increases as reported in Fig. 6. Vice versa, at high engine speeds, the PM is mainly constituted by soot.

Fig. 5: Soot and SOF concentration of the samples collected before the DPF for the different engine conditions investigated.

Fig. 6: History of in-cylinder pressure, injector current, and rate of heat release for two engine speeds of the FIC at FL

In Fig. 6 the in-cylinder combustion behavior is reported as an example for low (2000 rpm) and high (3000 rpm) engine speeds. It is possible to observe a regime change in the injection current signals, and following, in the combustion development. Indeed, at low rpm a triple injection mode occurs, whereas at high rpm a single injection is performed by the ECU of the engine. Consequently, the in-cylinder combustion and rate of heat release (ROHR) at 2000 rpm, the multi-injection case, present a quick decreasing rate of the diffusive combustion with respect to the case with one injection. This combustion behavior probably cause the strong increase of soot production (4 times higher) at 3000 and 3500 rpm in Fig. 5.

In order to analyze the chemical composition of the soot emitted at full load, the GC-MS technique allows detecting qualitatively and quantitatively the PAH up to 300 u present in the DCM soluble organic fraction. This fraction includes both the PAH adsorbed on soot and the PAH condensed from the gas phase, as described in the experimental section. The total PAH concentration before and after the abatement systems is reported in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7: Total PAH concentration of samples collected before after-treatment systems and after DPF and SCR.

Fig. 8: PAH concentration distributions in the samples collected after the SCR, at the different engine speeds.

In general, the total PAH concentration increases with engine speed due to the increasing quantity of injected fuel. In particular, at engine out, high levels of PAH is noted; it is linked to the in-cylinder combustion development and the burning of flames in rich fuel condition at higher engine speeds. The PAH abatement efficiency is obviously high toward the diesel oxidation catalyst and the DPF.

The highest conversion efficiency was detected @ 3500rpm and it is greater than 90%. An interestingly result was noted after the SCR and the ammonia reduction system. In particular, a sharp increase in the PAH concentration was noted. It could be linked with the volatile composition of particles.

The PAH distribution reported in Fig.8 revealed an enrichment in high molecular weight PAH when the engine speed is increased in agreement with the previous discussion [7]. In particular, Fluoranthene, Pyrene, Benzo[ghi]fluoranthene, Benzo(a)anthracene, Benzo(b)fluoranthene, Benzo(k)fluoranthene, Benzo(a)pyrene were well recognize, and the latter three high aromatics compounds were noted with higher intensity at higher engine speed.

Since the individual PAH compounds are not equally toxic, from environmental and toxicological points of view more interesting than the total PAHs concentration is the evaluation of the carcinogenicity of the exhaust emissions, which is indicated by the benz(a)pyrene-equivalent (BaP_{eq}) concentration [8]. The BaP_{eq} for the exhaust after the SCR, calculated taking into account for all the GC-MS detected PAHs, is reported in the inset of Fig.8. It is possible to observe that BaP_{eq} and, therefore, the toxicity, increases with the engine speed increase. The highest value is reached at 3000rpm.

Fig. 9: Fluorescence spectra in DCM at $\lambda_{exc}=266\text{nm}$ of the samples collected after the SCR, at the different engine speeds.

In Fig. 9 the spectra intensity and shape in the UV-visible range confirm the presence of a heavier molecular weight fraction in the SOF with mainly aromatic character. In particular, considering that the fluorescence emission is progressively shifted toward the visible when the number of aromatic rings increases [10], it is possible to assert that, with the increasing of the engine speed, the spectra shape change toward heavier aromatic moieties.

Fig. 10: UV-visible absorption spectra in DCM of the samples collected after the SCR, at the different engine speeds.

In previous works [8, 9], it was found that the PAH was only a fraction of DCM soluble extracted from soot formed in combustion systems. There is also a higher molecular weight fraction, not detectable by GC-MS, which can be as toxic as the lighter PAH, or even more, and has a role in soot inception too. This heavier fraction

presents mainly an aromatic character, therefore in the present paper it was investigated by UV-visible spectroscopic techniques. In Figs. 9 and 10 the fluorescence and absorption spectra, respectively, of the exhaust collected at the SCR exit have been reported, normalized for the Normal liter sampled.

The absorption spectra (Fig.10) presented a fine structure typical of PAH, with a main large peak located in the UV and a relevant number of minor peaks located in the visible portion of the spectrum, [11] but superimposed on an unstructured background, due to the heavier fraction of SOF. The fine structure is much more evident at 3000 rpm, with respect to the other engine conditions, in agreement with the higher PAH concentration found by GC-MS (Fig.5). The main peak at 260 nm in the spectra can be due to the fuel absorption [9], as suggested also by its higher intensity at 3000 rpm, when the fuel consumption is higher. The increase of the absorption and fluorescence intensity with rpm, suggests a parallel increase of the high molecular weight fraction concentration, differently from the concentration trend of PAHs (Fig.4), which presents a maximum at 3000 rpm.

In order to characterize the physical nature of the particles emitted by the engine and flowing through the EATS, the particle size and number were measured via the DMS500. In Fig. 11, the particle size function distribution and the particles number are reported for the full load engine operation at different engine speeds: 1600, 2000, 3000, 3500 rpm, respectively. Measurements are displayed for each engine speed reporting the data of the particle size function distributions upstream (before) DPF (B-DPF), immediately after the DPF (A-DPF) and after the SCR (A-SCR). The vertical dotted lines show the limits of the particle size range from 10 to 23 nm.

Particles detected at engine out, prior to enter the DPF (all the blue continuous lines), are characterized by a bimodal distribution with a high concentration of particles in both nucleation and accumulation modes [12]. The highest PN in nucleation mode was measured at 1600 rpm; while, in accumulation mode, at 3500 rpm. In particular, moving from low to high engine speed the PN peak shifts towards larger diameters. Moreover, PN are detected in the whole size range 5-400nm.

The overall physical characteristics are mainly related to the high injection pressure and the combustion behavior. In fact, at full load operation, no EGR is activated and the engine works at the highest performance. The higher the engine speed, the higher the mass flow rate of intake air and the fuel consumption. As already showed in Fig. 6, the in-cylinder pressure, rate of heat release and injector drive current change moving toward higher engine speed. The injection takes place into the cylinder with three events up to 2500 rpm, above which only one injection is performed. Injections occurred at very high pressure that guarantee a good atomization of the fuel, even at high engine speed, where the time to develop the combustion is reduced. Multi-injection strategy allowed to deliver the fuel in three different events, it means the fuel is injected at different times during the compression stroke, it has enough time to evaporate and mixes with the fresh air guaranteeing good combustion efficiency (up to 42% at 2000 rpm) [13]. Increasing the engine speed, the time to develop good mixture, efficient combustion and in-cylinder reduction of pollutants is reduced.

Fig. 11: Particle size function distributions @ FL for different engine speeds, B-DPF, A-DPF and A-SCR

In Fig. 11, when the multi-injection is deactivated there are no improvement of combustion due to pilot injections and, as consequence, the particles at the raw exhaust are large in number and have big diameter. Moreover, the possibility to realize a combustion with multi-injections enables a lower engine out temperature. Once the engine passes the 2500 rpm, the temperature increases by approximately 40°C, up to a maximum temperature of 530°C (Fig. Page 6 of 9

4). Finally, high in-cylinder temperature improve the particles oxidation and the reduction of small particles could be more effective than the bigger ones. This behavior is also linked to the ROHR development into the cylinder. It is noted larger diffusive combustion at 3000 and 3500 rpm.

After DPF, passing through the DOC/DPF system the exhaust gas increases its temperature due to the oxidation catalyst reactions that occur in the DOC, while the particles number is strongly reduced in the DPF. In the DOC exothermic reaction of the gases oxidize the CO and HC, NO into NO₂, and particulate matter. Due to the high temperature into the DPF the PM oxidation takes place with NO₂ and O₂, passive regeneration. Therefore, particles are **intercepted** by the trap but could also be produced by the passive filter regeneration. Looking at the particles size function distribution after the DPF in Fig. 11, bimodal distribution is more evident; particles in the range 10-23 nm are reduced in number more than the bigger ones. Probably, the high number of nano-particles B-DPF at medium engine speed contributes to form greater agglomerated particles A-DPF even if in minor number concentration. Passive regeneration contributes to the agglomeration mode too.

After SCR, the exhaust gas moves from the DPF out toward the SCR in a one meter long pipe where urea is injected (half way along the pipe) and mixed with the hot gas. In the SCR, NO_x are reduced via reactions occurring at temperature greater than 400°C. These reactions could produce emission of NH₃ and for this reason a clean-up catalytic converter (CUC) is placed on the outlet of the SCR. Tests on the exhaust gases prior to entering the SCR could not be performed due to the high amount of urea in the flow as this can damage the measurement system. After the SCR, the engine is provided with a NH₃ sensor to avoid emissions of high concentrations of ammonia. This allows particulate measurements to be taken at this position. In general, the particles emitted A-SCR are reduced in number and in the range 10-23 nm with a signal to noise ratio around one. This behavior was recognized for all the tested points and could be due to the high temperature in the system, up to 500°C prior the SCR, and the presence of ammonia. Other authors already reported interaction of exhaust gas and particles with the reactions occurring in the SCR [14, 15].

In order to follow both number and diameter of particles, Fig. 12 shows a bubble graph of total particle number vs. engine speed. The diameter of the bubbles in the plot are proportional to the computed mean diameter (electrical mobility equivalent diameter). The value of the mean diameter is reported too. Due to the bimodal characteristics of the function distribution showed in Fig. 11, two mean diameters were computed: one for the particles falling in the range 10-23 nm, and the second for the particles with diameter greater than 23 nm.

The particles number (PN) and mean diameters are reported sweeping the engine speed. B-DPF, particles in the nucleation mode ranges from 14.6 to 16.6 are seen; A-DPF, a wider range is detected (15.3-18.5nm). A-SCR, the particles are bigger than those at the engine out (16.5-18.3nm). For particles in accumulation mode, B-DPF very small diameters were measured; 48-60nm. A-DPF, bigger diameters are measured; 71-88 nm. A-SCR, smaller particles of 81-63 nm are observed. All the measured mean diameters are lower than 100 nm, and bigger than 14 nm.

Fig. 12: Total particle number and mean particle diameters for different engine speeds at full load

A-SCR, at Full Load the maximum quantity of urea is injected. From the comparison A-DPF vs A-SCR, it can be assumed that with urea injection probably some reactions occur in the catalyst. As a result, the particles smaller than 23 nm decrease both in diameter and in number. The particles larger than 23 nm increase in diameter, even strongly in some cases (i.e. 3500 rpm) and decrease in number. The reactions that occur in the SCR system seem to support an agglomeration of particles.

Fig. 13: DPF filtration efficiency of the FIC engine at Full Load for different engine speeds

Fig. 13 shows DPF filtration efficiency for particles <23nm, >23nm, and total (all particulates), vs. engine speed, at full load. Efficiency of the DPF is very high with particles below 23 nm, it ranges between 96.5% and 99.4%. For bigger particles, lower efficiency was noted, 82.6%-95.8%. This affected the total efficiency; the lowest was recognized at 2000 rpm, 88%. The DPF is more efficient at collecting <23nm particles than those >23nm.

Summary/Conclusions

Results showed that the abatement efficiency of soot after DPF and SCR systems, at all engine speeds, is very high (around 90% or more), as evaluated gravimetrically and by mobility analyzer, which discriminates also among the different dimensional ranges of particles. The DPF is more efficient at collecting <23nm particles whereas in the SCR system particles are subjected to reactions which seem to support an agglomeration of particles, with beneficial effect on the harmfulness to human health. For PAH the abatement efficiency is lower with respect to soot, but it increases at higher engine speeds, when the concentration is much higher.

Higher molecular weight species, mainly aromatics, are also formed in concentration at exhaust higher with respect to PAH and their detection is important because they could be soot precursors and could also have an intrinsic toxicity, comparable or also higher with respect to PAH. These species are not detectable by GC-MS and spectroscopic techniques have been employed in the present work for their analysis. It was found a large increase of the heavy aromatic species concentration with engine speed.

References

1. www.downtoten.com [Accessed 01 July 2019]
2. www.sureal-23.cperi.certh.gr [Accessed 01 July 2019]
3. www.pems4nano.eu [Accessed 01 July 2019]
4. www.dieper-project.eu [Accessed 01 July 2019]
5. World Health Organization. Review of evidence on health aspects of air pollution-REVIHAAP Project; WHO Regional Office for Europe: Copenhagen, Denmark, 2013.
6. Giechaskiel, B., Lahde, T., Suarez-Bertoa, R. et al. "Particle number measurements in the European legislation and future JRC activities". Combustion Engines. 174(3), 3-16, 2018. DOI: 10.19206/CE-2018-301.

7. EPA. (United States, E. P. A.: Water-related environmental fate of 129 priority pollutants. EPA Publication EPA-440/4-79-029a (Volume I) and EPA-440/4-79- 029b (Volume II), Office of Water Planning and Standards, Washington, D.C, 1979
8. Ciajolo, A., Barbella, R., Tregrossi, A., Bonfanti, L., "Spectroscopic and compositional signatures of pah-loaded mixtures in the soot inception region of a premixed ethylene flame" Proc. Comb. Inst. 27: 1481-1487 (1998).
9. Apicella, B., Mancarusu, E., Russo, C., Tregrossi, A., Oliano, M. M., Ciajolo, A., Vaglieco, B.M., "Effect of After-Treatment Systems on Organic Particulate Matter Emissions in Diesel Engine Exhaust" Proceeding of the Mediterranean Combustion Symposium, MCS11 Tenerife, Spain, 16-20 June 2019.
10. Berلمان, I. "Handbook of florescence spectra of aromatic molecules". Elsevier, 1971.
11. Tregrossi, A., Apicella, B., Ciajolo, A. Russo, C. "Fast analysis of PAH in complex organic carbon mixtures by reconstruction of UV-Visible spectra", Chem. Eng. Trans., 57: 1447-1452, 2017.
12. Kittelson, D.B. 1998. "Engines and Nanoparticles: A Review," J. Aerosol Sci., Vol. 29, No. 5/6, pp. 575-588, 1998
13. Mancarusu, E. Merola, S.S., Vaglieco, B.M. "Study of the multi-injection combustion process in a transparent direct injection common rail diesel engine by means of optical techniques" International Journal of Engine Research 9(6):483-498, 2008 DOI: 10.1243/14680874JER01308
14. Amanatidis, S., Ntziachristos, L., Giechaskiel, B., Bergmann, A., Smaras, Z., "Impact of Selective Catalytic Reduction on Exhaust Particle Formation over Excess Ammonia Events". Environ. Sci. Technol. 48 (19), pp 11527–11534, 2014. DOI: 10.1021/es502895v
15. Czerwinski, J., Zimmerli, Y., Mayer, A, Lemaire, J. Zurcher, D, D'Urbano, G, "Investigation of SDPF-Diesel Particle Filter with SCR Coating for HD-Applications". SAE Paper 2015-01-1023, 2015

Contact Information

Ezio Mancarusu

Researcher at Istituto Motori CNR

Via G. Marconi, 4, 80125, Napoli, Italy.

e.mancarusu@im.cnr.it

www.im.cnr.it

Acknowledgments

This work was funded in the framework of the European Commission Horizon 2020 dieper project (Grant agreement no.: 723976), on the diesel efficiency improvement with Particulates and emission reduction. The authors would like to thank Ing. Alessandro di Gaeta, and Ing. Veniero Giglio for participating in the experimental campaign; Carlo Rossi and Bruno Sgammato for their technical support; the partners of this project for their valuable input.

Definitions/Abbreviations

BC	BlackCarbon
CI	Condensation Particle Counter
DMA	Differential Mobility Analyzer
MS	Differential Mobility Spectrometer
DOC	Diesel Oxidation Catalyst
DPF	Diesel Particulate Filter
DR	Dilution Ratio
EC	Europe Commission
ECU	Electronic Control Unit
EATS	Exhaust After Treatment System
FL	Full load
FSN	Filter Smoke Number
GC/MS	Gas Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry
LD	Light-Duty
NDIR	Non-Dispersive Infrared
NEDC	New European Driving Cycle
OBD	On-Board Diagnostics
OC	Organic Carbon
OM	Organic Matter
PAH	PolyAromatic Hydrocarbons
PEMS	portable emissions measurement systems
PM	Particulate Matter
PMP	Particle Measurement Program
PMR	Power to Mass Ratio
RDE	Real-World Conditions
RPM	Revolution Per Minutes
SCR	Selective Catalytic Reduction
SOF	Soluble Organic Fraction

WHSC

Worldwide Harmonized Steady
State Cycle

WLTP

Worldwide Harmonized Light-Duty
Test Procedure

WHTC

Worldwide Harmonized Transient
Driving Cycle